

MODEL OF FORMATION OF PHYSICAL FITNESS OF MILITARY ATHLETES OF DIFFERENT DIRECTIONS

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Annotation: The article analyzes the features of the training process within various types of military sports, such as shooting, combat sambo, applied military sports and others. Based on modern scientific research in the field of physical training and military sports, the authors propose a comprehensive model that takes into account the individual characteristics of athletes and the requirements of their specialization. The proposed model can be an effective tool for coaches and specialists in the field of physical training of military athletes, helping them achieve high results in their activities.

Key words: physical training, military athletes, formation model, multidirectionality, training process, military sports, specialization, training methods, physical exercises, sports results.

Introduction. Physical fitness plays a key role in the success of military athletes, since effectiveness in combat situations directly depends on a high level of physical fitness [3]. In the modern world, where demands on military specialists are constantly growing, it is important to develop effective methods for developing physical fitness that take into account the various specializations of military athletes [1, 2].

However, different types of military sports have their own unique physical fitness requirements. For example, shooting training requires high accuracy and stability, while combat sambo requires strength, flexibility and endurance. This creates a need for individualized approaches to the training process [4, 5].

Thus, the development of a model for the formation of physical fitness for multi-directional military athletes is an urgent task. The proposed model will make it possible to optimize training programs adapted to the specifics of each military discipline, which will ultimately lead to improved athletic performance and effectiveness of actions in combat conditions. In this context, our article makes an important contribution to the development of military sports and improving the training of military athletes [6].

The purpose of this article is to develop a comprehensive model of physical fitness formation for multi-directional military athletes. We strive to explore modern methods and principles of the training process that take into account the specific requirements of various types of military sports. Our goal is to create a universal model that will be adapted to specific sports areas, such as shooting, hand-to-hand combat, martial arts and others, taking into account the characteristics of each discipline. The proposed model should help coaches and specialists in the field of physical training of military athletes to develop effective training programs that contribute to achieving high sports results and increasing the effectiveness of actions in combat conditions.

The practical significance of this article is as follows:

- Optimization of the training process: The developed model for the formation of physical fitness will allow coaches and specialists in the field of physical training of military athletes to create individualized and effective training programs, taking into account the specifics of each military discipline.
- Improving sports performance: The application of the proposed model will allow military athletes to achieve high sports results by improving their physical fitness in accordance with the requirements of their specialization.
- Increased effectiveness in combat conditions: Improving the physical fitness of military athletes not only contributes to the achievement of high results in competitions, but also increases their effectiveness in carrying out military tasks and actions in combat conditions due to improved physical qualities and skills.

- Promotion of military sports: The development of effective methods for developing the physical fitness of military athletes contributes to the promotion and development of military sports as an important component of military training, and also draws attention to the importance of sports training for the successful completion of combat missions.

Research results and discussion. Among the modern methods of developing the physical fitness of military athletes, the following stand out:

Based on the principles of functional anatomy and biomechanics, this method involves performing exercises that simulate the movements characteristic of specific military tasks. Functional training helps develop not only strength and endurance, but also coordination of movements, which is important for effective combat operations.

This method involves alternating high-intensity exercise with periods of rest and is effective in increasing aerobic and anaerobic endurance, as well as promoting fat loss and improving overall fitness.

Bodyweight Training: This training method is based on using your own body weight as the main load. It allows you to develop strength, flexibility and endurance without the need for special equipment.

Functional training using machines: This method involves performing functional exercises using specialized machines. It provides more precise targeted development of certain muscle groups and movements, which is important for the formation of specific military sports skills.

Key steps in developing a comprehensive readiness model include:

	Development stage	Description
	Needs analysis:	Assessment of physical fitness requirements for a specific sports discipline or sports. This includes studying the

		characteristics of the competition, typical movements, loads and physical qualities required.
	Identification of key components:	Determination of the main aspects of physical fitness necessary for successful completion of tasks in the chosen discipline. This may include strength, endurance, speed, flexibility, coordination, reaction and other aspects.
	Development of training programs:	Creation of individualized training programs aimed at developing each of the key components of physical fitness. These programs must be tailored to each athlete's individual needs and abilities.
	Consideration of training principles:	Using fundamental training principles such as progressive overload, periodization, individualization and variability to optimize the training process and achieve maximum results.
	Evaluation and correction:	Conducting regular assessments of the effectiveness of training programs and the model as a whole. Make adjustments and improvements as necessary to optimize results.
	Implementation into practice:	Practical application of the developed model in the training process of athletes and coaching. Ensuring control over its implementation and adaptation to changing conditions and needs of athletes.

The development of a comprehensive model of preparedness formation allows us to provide a systematic and effective approach to the training process, which contributes to the achievement of high results in sports.

The practical application of the model of physical fitness formation plays a key role in achieving high sports results in athletes. This includes not only the development

of an appropriate model, but also its implementation in the training process, as well as evaluation of effectiveness for further improvement.

After developing a model for the formation of physical fitness, it is introduced into the training process of athletes. This includes the development of individualized training programs based on the principles of the model and their subsequent application in training practice.

After a certain period of application of the model, the results are evaluated. Assessment can be carried out through:

By comparing current sports results with previous indicators, the effectiveness of the model can be assessed.

Conducting specific tests to assess changes in athletes' physical fitness (for example, endurance, strength, speed and flexibility tests).

Feedback from athletes and coaches: Collect feedback and opinions on the use of the model from athletes and coaches to identify its effectiveness and possible improvements.

The practical application of the model of physical fitness formation and evaluation of results play an important role in achieving sports goals. Consistent and systematic application of the model, as well as analysis of the results obtained, help optimize the training process and achieve maximum efficiency in training athletes. Practical recommendations: Individualization of programs: Develop individualized training programs for each athlete, taking into account his individual characteristics, level of preparedness and the specifics of the military discipline in which he is engaged.

Training Variability: Include a variety of exercises and techniques in the training process to develop all the necessary physical qualities of athletes and prevent training monotony.

Systematic: Maintain a systematic training process by following specific training cycles and periods to achieve your goals.

Progressive Load: Gradually increase the load in the training process, taking into account the body's adaptation capabilities and preventing overtraining and injury.

Feedback: Maintain open communication with coaches and athletes, collect feedback on the effectiveness of training programs and make adjustments as necessary.

Conclusions. The development of a model for the formation of physical fitness for multi-directional military athletes plays a key role in achieving high sports results and increasing the effectiveness of the training process. Individualization of programs, variability of training, systematicity and progressive load are the main principles on which the model of preparedness development should be based. Constant feedback and program adjustments based on assessment results help optimize the training process and ensure military athletes are as prepared as possible to perform their duties and achieve athletic success.

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